

MEASURING EFFICIENCY OF LOGISTICS PROCESSES IN DISTRIBUTION CENTERS

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ANNOTATION This work is to represent a new approach to measuring, estimating and monitoring the efficiency of the logistics processes in the distribution center of a trading company. The purpose of this work is to represent the developed methodology manner, encompassing three main parts:

1. The analysis and decomposition of the logistics subsystems, processes and activities in the distribution center.
2. The process of defining and choosing key variables and indicators of the logistics systems and transport and warehouse subsystems.
3. The model of measuring and monitoring the operative and qualitative efficiency of the distribution center.

The goal of the developed and represented manner is to create the suitable bases to enhance the overall efficiency of the processes in the distribution center.

Keywords: Efficiency, Quality, Logistics Processes, Distribution Centres, Multiple Objective Data Envelopment Analysis (MODEA)

Methodology: The Multiple Objective Data Envelopment Analysis (MODEA) approach has been applied in this work, and this approach in an adequate manner treats the problems of common resources and goal conflicts between different subsystems and entities.

The obtained results indicate the different impact of the transport and warehouse subsystems performances upon the overall efficiency of the distribution center, as well as the suitability of applying the MODEA approach for measuring the efficiency of the logistics systems.

As opposed to the traditional approaches to the efficiency measuring, the represented manner joins the indicators of the economic and qualitative efficiency,

and in an adequate way perceives the problems of the efficient exploitation of the common resources.

Introduction

Modern business operations primarily entail tremendously demanding market struggle, no matter whether it is about production or service rendering in any industry branch. In order to survive in the market and achieve profitability the companies have to be efficient. The efficiency represents an extremely significant indicator for the analysis and bringing important conclusions on the business operations of the companies. There is no universal and generally accepted definition of the efficiency. Different authors define efficiency in different ways. Gleason and Barnum (1982) under the notion of effectiveness means the level of the goals accomplishment ("doing the right things"), while under the notion of efficiency they mean the accomplishment of these goals in the best possible way ("doing the right things in the right way"), that is to say accomplishing the largest number of outputs while using the least amount of resources. In the past, both in literature and in practice, the greatest attention was paid to the operational efficiency. Operational efficiency can be defined as the ratio between the exploited resources and the accomplished results.

Results and Discussion

In this work, the efficiency of 20 DC and its transport and warehouse subsystems has been analyzed. The set of the observed DC can be deemed homogenous due to the fact this DC operate in the same way and under the same conditions. The efficiency estimation has been carried out by applying the CCR DEA and MODEA approaches. The DC efficiency variables, by applying different approaches, have been represented in the table 2. The first three models refer to the MODEA approach, in which the coefficient φ (closeness parameter) takes the variables of 10%, 20% and 50%. By comparing the number of DC efficiencies obtained by applying the MODEA and CCR DEA approaches, it is pointed to a considerably larger number of efficient DMU by applying the latter approach. This can be explained by the fact that CCR model joins all indicators into a unique

measure of efficiency with no separation or observation of the efficiency of its subsystems, that is to say it “overrates” the efficiency of DC.

Table 1: DC Efficiency

<i>DMU</i>	<i>MODEA</i>			<i>CCR</i>
	<i>10%</i>	<i>20%</i>	<i>50%</i>	
DMU 1	0.9783	0.9837	0.9997	1.0000
DMU 2	2.0000	2.0000	2.0000	1.0000
DMU 3	1.7778	1.7969	1.7969	1.0000
DMU 4	0.6835	0.6911	0.6951	0.4783
DMU 5	0.5022	0.5177	0.5379	0.3704
DMU 6	0.7862	0.7923	0.8051	0.6182
DMU 7	1.5490	1.5832	1.6336	0.9496
DMU 8	0.7859	0.7931	0.8149	0.5650
DMU 9	1.0605	1.0718	1.1087	0.6912
DMU 10	1.0524	1.0577	1.0736	0.7153
DMU 11	1.4337	1.4961	1.6667	1.0000
DMU 12	2.0000	2.0000	2.0000	1.0000
DMU 13	0.6147	0.6216	0.6240	0.5063
DMU 14	0.3101	0.3175	0.3180	0.2289
DMU 15	1.6086	1.6086	1.6097	1.0000
DMU 16	1.6267	1.6349	1.6594	1.0000
DMU 17	2.0000	2.0000	2.0000	1.0000
DMU 18	0.3523	0.3554	0.3554	0.1921
DMU 19	1.0539	1.0948	1.2194	1.0000
DMU 20	0.5993	0.5993	0.6045	0.4670
<i>Average efficiency</i>	<i>1.1388</i>	<i>1.1508</i>	<i>1.1761</i>	<i>0.7391</i>

<i>Efficient</i> DMUs	3 (15%)	3 (15%)	3(15%)	9 (45%)
<i>Inefficient</i> DMUs	17 (85%)	17 (85%)	17(85%)	11 (55%)

By applying the MODEA approach, it can be obtained only 15% efficient DC, while CCR approach yields even 45% efficient DC (table 2). Such results can be explained by the fact that CCR model does not take into consideration the efficiency of subsystems in DC. On the other hand, acc. to MODEA approach, DC is efficient if the transport and warehouse subsystems are efficient. The average efficiency of DC by applying MODEA approach for $\alpha = 10\%$ amounts to 1.1388 (table 2) with the average efficiency of warehouse subsystem amounting to 0.5158, and transport one to 0.6229. The observed DC set can be considered as relatively inefficient and the largest portion of this inefficiency is a consequence of the warehouse subsystem inefficiency.

Efficiency of one DC subsystem (warehouse or transport one) does not entail the DC efficiency. Based upon the table 3, it can easily be concluded that warehouse subsystem efficiencies are smaller than the transport subsystem efficiencies regardless of the variable of the parameter φ . By analyzing the obtained variables, it can be concluded that there is a certain number of DC whose subsystems do not change the efficiency regardless of the approach. DMU 2, DMU 12 and DMU 17 represent DC with stable performances and which are efficient according to both the MODEA and the CCR DEA approach. Stable efficiency of these centres can be explained by a relatively small quantity of the used resources for the realization of a great number of deliveries over 7000 (considerably higher than average), with the number of errors in the transport and warehouse subsystems DMU 2 and DMU 12 considerably lower than average.

Figure 1: Efficiency of DC and its subsystem

By analyzing table 3 and figure 4 in more detail, three characteristic DC groups can be selected. The first group is comprised of the formerly mentioned efficient units. This group includes DMU2, DMU 12 and DMU 17 whose transport and warehouse subsystems are efficient. The second group includes the units whose warehouse subsystem is significantly more efficient than the transport subsystems. Such units are DMU 1 and DMU 11. As opposed to them, DMU 3, DMU 6, DMU

8, DMU 9 and DMU 13 have significantly more efficient transport subsystems. The last two DC groups, apart from inefficiency of at least one subsystem are characterized by the overall DC inefficiency. This confirms the claim that no DC can be efficient if one of its subsystems is inefficient.

Conclusion

In the conditions of market economy and strong competition, companies have to be ready for development and application of the widest range of methods, models and techniques, by means of which to enhance their business system, all with the aim of winning a strong enough position in the market. The modern customer does not wait to satisfy their own need. This is why the readiness of the company to respond to any demand on the part of the customer has to be at the highest level. Measuring DC efficiency, as well as determining the influence of certain subsystems, processes and activities upon the overall efficiency, over the recent years, has become an extremely important task.

The model proposed in this paper illustrates the significance and influence of subsystems efficiency upon the overall DC efficiency. The significance of the model is reflected in the fact that the model simultaneously measures the efficiency of DC, that is to say its warehouse and transport subsystem, including the indicators of both the operational and qualitative efficiency. The application of this model can produce useful information on the organizational changes which may influence the costs reduction and increase in the quality of services. The illustrated model represents the basic model which may further be built upon, perfected and used to multiple purposes. Above all, it represents assistance to DC managers in the decision making process. Apart from this, the model, with minimal corrections, can be used to estimate the efficiency of other logistics systems and supply chains. The model, also, represents assistance to the decision makers in the process of choosing logistics providers.

In literature, there is a lack of case studies, that is model testing in the concrete DC examples. This fact indicates the insufficient amount of researches in this area.

The efficiency of supply chains is also influenced by a great number of factors upon which the company management have no influence. In future models, it would be desirable to introduce certain indicators which, to a certain extent, can describe external factors such as: weather conditions, market situation, competition behavior, etc.

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